

THE ROLE OF DEVELOPMENTAL GAMES IN TEACHING JUNIOR SCHOOL CHILDREN

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ABSTRACT

The article reveals the importance of developing 4K skills and identifies ways to develop younger schoolchildren in gaming activities. The possibilities of gaming activities in the formation of 4K skills (this is a concept according to which a child should develop four skills: communication, cooperation, creativity and critical thinking) in primary schoolchildren have been identified.

The need of modern society for the harmonious development of the individual places new demands on the education system. The task of modern education is to educate citizens who are able to think, independently “discover” knowledge, quickly navigate the flow of information, and are able to find the right solution in a situation of choice. The implementation of this task objectively requires a qualitatively new approach to teaching and raising children. Education should be developmental, enrich the child with knowledge and methods of mental activity, form creativity and communication abilities. Particular attention should be paid to the primary education system as the most important stage of lifelong learning, stimulating the development of children, providing them with effective programs for the development of creative and intellectual abilities.

Their further development and education, as well as the formation of the child’s personality, largely depend on the upbringing of children at primary school age. An important prerequisite for the successful education of junior schoolchildren in secondary schools is the development of 4K skills.

It should be noted that in the modern education system the priority subject is the individual with his needs, interests, properties and individual characteristics. In this regard, there is an increasingly active transition from a knowledge-based to a person-oriented paradigm education, therefore, the focus of the educational process of a preschool educational institution on the development of preschool children becomes an urgent problem. This importance is also due to the requirements reflected in government documents (Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Education”, State Program for the Development of Education and Science in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026).

The problem of developing 4K skills in younger schoolchildren is one of the most pressing in child psychology, since human interaction with the outside world is possible thanks to his activity and activity; in addition, activity is an indispensable prerequisite for the formation of the mental qualities of an individual, his independence and initiative. And therefore, now, modern programs provide for the formation in younger schoolchildren not of individual fragmentary "lightweight" knowledge about the world around them, but of completely reliable elementary systems of ideas about the various properties and relationships of objects and phenomena. One of the leading experts in the field of mental education of preschool children, N.N. Poddyakov also rightly emphasizes that at the present stage it is necessary to give children the key to understanding reality, and not strive for an exhaustive amount of knowledge, as was the case in the traditional system of mental education. The 4K skills development methodology is designed to help prepare children of primary school age to master the basics of science. Particularly effective for this purpose will be the inclusion of children in play activities. Play activities for children of this age have not yet lost their relevance and are naturally used by primary school teachers for the development of students.

Often, despite the organization of gaming activities, this work is of a formal, situational nature; younger schoolchildren have a low level of creativity, critical thinking, communication skills and the ability to work in a team. As a result, the developmental opportunities of gaming activities remain unrealized in the practice of primary education. The lack of development of this problem in the psychological, pedagogical and methodological literature and the increased need for the development of creativity, critical thinking, communication skills and the ability to work in a team in gaming activities indicate the relevance of the study.

The importance of play in a child's life has long been appreciated by teachers and psychologists around the world; back in 1961, the International Association for the Protection of the Child's Right to Play (IRA) was created. The association has developed an international document "Declaration of the Child's Right to Play", which states that children are the foundation future, and the game is an integral part of this foundation:

- children played and play in all cultures and at all times;
- play, as well as the basic needs of nutrition, health, safety and education, is vital to the development of the potential of any child;
- play is a means of communication and self-expression that unites thought and action; the game gives a feeling of satisfaction and success;
- the game is instinctive, arbitrary and spontaneous; play helps children develop physically, intellectually, emotionally and socially;
- a game is a way to learn to live, and not just a pastime.

On the other hand, an analysis of practice shows that the game is losing its main position in the practice of modern preschool education. As noted by T.P. Avdulova, the potential of the game is not realized. This is due to a number of reasons of a pedagogical and psychological nature. First of all, in preschool institutions the emphasis has shifted towards teaching and organizing classes of a didactic nature, and modern preschoolers have no time left for free creative play. Children raised outside educational institutions are also busy with developmental activities, and play, as a rule, is not encouraged by their parents. In addition, "home" children are deprived of the company of peers, which provides ample opportunities for playful interactions.

This is how describes this situation A.V. Zaporozhets: "...games do not occupy sufficient space in educational work; games are poor in content and do not have the proper impact on the physical and mental development of preschool children. Serious mistakes are made in organizing and directing children's play activities. On the one hand, there are attempts to strictly regulate gaming activities, when the teacher imposes on children both the plot and the method of carrying out the game, turning it into an educational activity, depriving it of its independent character. On the other hand, some educators have a different kind of incorrect tendency to completely not interfere in children's play, to actually refuse to lead it, which negatively affects the formation of play activity and reduces its educational significance."

Skepticism about the value of play in the early years is further exacerbated by widespread myths promoted by hundreds of "smart kids" products. These children's products lead educators and parents to believe that the earlier children begin to master the basic elements of reading and writing, the more likely they are to succeed in school. Nothing could be further from the truth! Play for children is a creative, spontaneous, unpredictable and absolutely fun activity. Although play may seem like a frivolous activity, it is an important learning tool for young children. It makes a significant contribution to a child's cognitive, physical, emotional and social development. Play is a natural and best way for children to learn as they explore themselves and observe others at play and work. They are natural explorers who have the need and desire to explore their world through real-life experiences and natural habitats.

Play is the way children make meaning from the complex world in which we live. Play is a means by which children take risks, challenge themselves both physically and mentally, create something new, cope with fears and enjoy the moment by creating new meanings. Children grow, learn and even explore the world through play. Play is the basis for discovery, reasoning and thinking. When children are given the freedom to experiment, make mistakes, and then learn from those mistakes, they develop skills that will last a lifetime.

Children do not differentiate between play, study and work. Children are, by nature, playful. They love to play because play is an activity in which any child is open to expressing their point of view, ideas and thoughts.

Play allows children to use their creativity while developing imagination, dexterity and physical, cognitive and emotional strength. Play is very important for healthy brain development. As game researcher K. Gross noted, it serves as preparation for further serious activity; In play, a child, by practicing, improves his abilities, but it should be remembered that play is a serious thing. According to D.B. Elkonin, the game has four main functions for a person: means of the need-motivational sphere, means of cognition, means of developing mental actions and means of voluntary behavior.

It is through play that children at a very early age become involved and interact with the world around them. Play allows children to create and explore a world that they can master, conquering their fears while practicing adult roles, sometimes in combination with other children or adult caregivers. So D.B. Elkonin, considering the content of a children's game, noted that the content of this game is an adult, his activities and relationships with other people. The basic unit of children's play is the role of an adult, which the child takes on. In the content of their play, children reproduce the relationships of adults in work and social life, reproduce them with varying depths of comprehension and sometimes penetrate into the true social meaning of human labor. The plots of the games are determined by the specific social conditions

of children's lives. As children make sense of their world, play helps them develop new competencies that lead to increased confidence and resilience they will need to meet future challenges. As Szucs D. noted in their study, free play allows children to learn to work in teams, share information, negotiate, resolve conflicts and master self-defense skills. Children practice decision-making skills through play, move at their own pace, and discover their own areas of interest.

Ideally, most play involves adults, but when play is controlled by adults, children give in to adult rules and lose some of the benefits that, what play gives them, especially in developing creativity, leadership and group skills. Unlike passive entertainment, play builds an active, healthy body. In fact, it has been suggested that encouraging unstructured play may be an exceptional way to increase activity levels in children. Above all, play is a simple joy that is a cherished part of childhood.

Play is an integral part of the academic environment. Play has been shown to help children adapt to the school environment and even improve their readiness to learn, learning behavior and problem-solving skills. Free play time and opportunities for peer interaction are important components of social-emotional learning.

Didactic educational games are only elements of purposefully organized and directed educational process. Most often, an adult organizes, leads and directs the game, but with traditional games this task can be assigned to an older child or one of the peers who knows the content of the game and has mastered the method of playing.

Today, play and the educational process are interconnected, taking into account the fact that play as an activity is of great interest to children and motivates them. The teacher must cooperate with the children in the game; he should help them by suggesting a problem, not by giving final solutions. In addition, he must help them realize their capabilities - to become a partner in the game.

Education through play means channeling the child's psychophysical potentials, but at the same time, play should be considered as the basis of the child's creativity and spontaneity. Through the activities of didactic games, children receive organized and creative motivation; in accordance with their abilities, they learn about the world around them, their mental and other abilities and characteristics. Didactic game is a form through which children update, distribute, test and consolidate their experience and its capabilities in an interesting way, and the acquired knowledge, experience and impressions are expressed and applied in new life and educational situations. Didactic games contribute to the overall development of the child, they direct his attention when it comes to the perception and observation of an object, when similarities and differences are compared, and encourage imagination and creativity. The content of didactic games expands children's overall picture of the world, guides their curiosity, encourages their speech activity, enriches their vocabulary and stimulates oral communication.

Using specially structured games (logical mathematical) the child develops critical thinking and creates special learning situations in which he masters intellectual processes: serialization, classification, numerical construction, construction in time and space, etc. Children's play deeply influences children and transforms them into responsible and well-adjusted adults.

When educators observe their children at play or join them in children's play, they gain a unique opportunity to see the world from their child's perspective as the child navigates a world perfectly designed just to suit his or her needs. Educators who have the opportunity to peer

into their children's world learn to communicate more effectively with their children and are given a different environment to offer them gentle, caring guidance. Children may be able to express their views, experiences and even frustrations through play, giving educators the opportunity to gain a more complete understanding of their point of view. Simply put, the game gives teachers an excellent opportunity to fully engage with their children.

In the education of primary school children, play and curriculum must be deeply integrated; Experienced teachers must be able to observe children's cognitive, social and physical learning occurring. A quality curriculum should be largely play-based.

In pedagogy, repeated attempts have been made to classify the organization of games. Games can be divided according to methods of organization: games under the guidance of a teacher; structured games; free games.

1. Teacher-led games - the teacher provides the material for the game, starts or joins the game in order to direct the game or give the child tips. This game usually gives the child guidance on what to do and when to do it. The game under the guidance of a teacher has a clear ending. This reduces the number of options for the development of events that may arise in the game, which is much easier for the child to understand. A clear game guide can help a child understand what steps, skills, actions and concepts are needed to achieve the game's ultimate goal. Features of teacher-led play - a low-stress play space for the child, where he can hone the skills he needs to play and interact with other children. Once the child has learned the steps necessary for the game, over time he plays the game without outside help.

2. Structured games are an activity or activity that has a specific goal to teach and develop a student certain life skill. Structured games include motor games and exercises (jumping, climbing), includes various types of games with water, paints, clay and other materials with their help, the child can indirectly express his desires and express his feelings in a non-directed form and experience a sense of achievement. A group of games belonging to the art therapy foundation (drawing with fingers, brushes, pastels, colored pencils).

3. Free play, which has no clear boundaries and rules, the child does what he wants. At the same time, the importance of this game lies in the development of children's communication with each other, it gives communication skills - discussion, resolution, conflict prevention, the ability to negotiate, etc.

The game, regardless of the method of organization, contributes to the development of the child's personal qualities, since they are formed in vigorous activity, which at each age stage becomes leading, determines his interests, attitude to reality, and the characteristics of relationships with other people. Already at early and junior age levels, it is in play that children have the greatest opportunity to be independent and creative. The older children become, the higher the level of their general development and education, the more significant is the pedagogical focus of the game on the formation of team and communication skills of children, on the development of critical thinking.

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